

Annexes

Annex 1: Supplement data to Open and Responsible

ROUND BEMS	FOCUS
<p>BEMS#1 July-August 2020 (virtual) Preliminary Session: Dual meeting WP2-WP6</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutual agreement on M&E activities • Monitoring and reflection on Mapping exercise (WP2) in view of design of territorial experiments and of mobilisation and preparation of territorial stakeholders (e.g., training on RRI/demand-driven innovation approach in health, WP3)
<p>BEMS#2 November-December 2020 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the preparation of the territorial experimentation with a focus on training on RRI/demand-drive approach and implementation of the need identification stage (preparation and launch of the Open Call for Needs) of the CHERRIES RRI Policy experiment (challenges, progresses, raising issues, future steps). • Self-reflection on the process of collaboration at territorial level and on local application of the CHERRIES Methodology for the need identification stage (learnings, critical issues)
<p>BEMS#3 January-February 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the implementation of the CHERRIES RRI Policy experiment, with reference to: a) the participatory process of identification of unmet needs and the application of RRI principles in the process of selection of the regional need; b) the preparation and Launch of the Open Call for Solutions (challenges, progresses, raising issues, future steps) • Self-reflection on the process of collaboration at territorial level and on local application of the CHERRIES Methodology for the need identification stage (learnings, critical issues) • Preparation and Launch of the Call for Proposal (timeline, target for the dissemination, reflection about the identification of solution providers within the territory and outside, raising issues) • Co-design of the Inter-Regional Reflection Workshop on RRI potential (T2.4): discussion about its arrangement (date; identification and recruitment of relevant stakeholders from each region; reflection on RRI aspects to deepen; COVID related issues to manage)
<p>BEMS#4 March-April 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the implementation of the territorial experimentation regarding the Solution selection stage (dissemination Open Call, set up of Selection Committee, application of RRI principles) (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Self-reflection on the process of collaboration at territorial level and on local application of the CHERRIES Methodology for the Solution Selection stage (learnings, critical issues) • Discussion of possible RRI aspects to deepen with regional stakeholders in the Inter-Regional reflection Workshop (discussion group)
<p>BEMS#5 May-June 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the implementation of the territorial experimentation regarding the Solution selection stage with a focus on the follow up of the Selection process and on the arrangement of management activities related to the sub-grant agreement negotiation, launch of the co-creation pilot, definition of the co-creation team and Plan of

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	<p>activities, design of the M&E system for local pilot and success criteria definition)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection on insights from the Inter-regional Reflection Workshop and RRI potential at the level of single institution and at territorial level • Agreement about the procedure for Mid-term evaluation exercise under T6.2 through the self-administration of an in-depth evaluation questionnaire by the local teams • Reflection about integration of RRI aspects in the co-creation process and activities of the innovation pilots and discussion of need of increasing of mutual learning exchanges among the three regions about co-creation experience • Evaluative exchange in view of the mid-term EU review
<p>BEMS#6 July-August 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the implementation of the territorial experimentation, with reference to the activation (launch) and ex-ante assessment of the Innovation co-creation Pilots (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Self-reflection on the process of collaboration at territorial level and on local application of the CHERRIES Methodology for the Solution Selection stage (learnings, critical issues) • Exchange on MT evaluation exercise (Q)
<p>BEMS#7 September-October 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the latest and ongoing activities and raising issues concerning the governance of the local experiment. Sharing of information and discussion about progresses and challenges/raising issues from the initial stage of implementation of the Co-creation pilot for the development of the “responsible” innovation solution. • Discussion and validation of main results from the Mid-term evaluation exercise (MTQ) in view of the finalisation of the 1st EDR (Experiment Diagnostic Report) • Reflection about raising issues and challenges regarding the definition of a M&E roadmap common to the three co-creation pilots • Discussion and agreement on next steps for M&E with reference to the planning of the ex-post evaluation exercise under T6.2. (administration of a second in-depth Questionnaire-EPQ and arrangement of ex-post evaluation visits on site in the three regions) and presentation of interconnection with T6.3 for OIA
<p>BEMS#8 December 2021 (virtual)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating on the implementation of the territorial experimentation with particular reference to the governance and monitoring of the co-creation pilots (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Self-reflection with local team about problems and challenges affecting the implementation of the co-creation pilot (regarding the process of collaboration and specific problems affecting the successful implementation of the co-creation Plan of activities) • Reflection about learnings from the GA implemented in Nicosia (Rep. of Cyprus) • Further step in the co-design process of the ex-post on-site visits (started during the GA in Nicosia) discussing and integrating main debriefings points from the regional WGs

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of next M&E steps under T6.3 (OIA) in view of the ex-post evaluation exercise
BEMS#9 February 2022 (virtual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update on the implementation of the territorial experimentation with particular reference to the co-creation pilots (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Mutual agreement on OIA plans and first evaluative conversation (T6.3) • Further step in co-designing of the three ex-post evaluation on-site visits
BEMS#10 March-April 2022 (virtual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update on the implementation of the territorial experimentation with particular reference to the co-creation pilots (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Preparation and co-design of the ex-post on-site visits
BEMS#11 June-July 2022 (virtual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update on the implementation of the territorial experimentation with particular reference to the co-creation pilots (challenges, progresses, lesson learned, raising issues, future steps) • Agreement for ex-post evaluation exercise (in-depth questionnaire) and discussion of the tentative agenda of the visit
BEMS#12 July-October 2022 (virtual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Last meeting on preparation of the on-site visits: compilation of the ex-post in-depth self-evaluation Q by local partners; discussion of the finalisation of the program and roles; co-design of activities planned (participative workshop, local events, plan of the meetings, coordination about role and activities for the final events)
BEMS#13 September-October 2022 (in-presence) *See also the following box regarding a related follow up session after the visit	(2 meetings during each visit) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening Session (BEMS#13/a) of the on-site visit with local core team of the RRI Policy experiments (integration of ex-post evaluation Q/gathering of evaluation knowledge) • Debriefing Session (BEMS#13/b) with core team at the end of the on-site visit
BEMS#13/A October 2022 (virtual) Not mandatory, arranged on request by local team of Örebro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow up Meeting with core team • Evaluative conversations with territorial actors not met during the on-site visit: Meeting with representatives of the co-creation Steering Group of the Laxå Pilot1 and Pilot 2 – reflection on lessons learned from the CHERRIES experience • Evaluative conversations with territorial actors not met during the on-site visit: Meeting with the Responsible of the Health Centre Laxå Municipality (co-creation team)
BEMS#14 January 2023 (virtual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation session of evaluation results reported in the regional chapters of the Final Evaluation Report

Table 1: List and focus of the bi-monthly evaluation and monitoring sessions considered in the Open and Responsible manuscript

Interviewee	Interviewee code
Senior official in Örebro County	I1
Senior official in Örebro County	I2
Senior official in Örebro County	I3

CEO of a Swedish CSO	I4
Senior official in Laxa municipality	I5
Innovation expert in Cyprus	I6
Senior official in Cyprus hospital	I7
Greek Healthcare innovator	I8
Representation of the PSI, Örebro	I9
Representative of Church in Örebro	I10
Senior Official in Örebro County	I11
Representative of local health centre in Örebro County	I12
Representative of CSO network in Örebro	I13
Entrepreneur Cyprus	I14
Greek Healthcare innovator	I15
Senior representative Ministry of research, Innovation and digital Policy, Cyprus	I16
Senior representative of the Cypriot Research and Innovation Foundation	I17
Healthcare professional Cyprus	I18
Representative of Cypriot CSO	I19
Senior management of Cypriot hospital	I20
Senior policy maker healthcare Örebro	I21
Senior policy maker regional development Örebro	I22

Table 2: Interviews considered in the Open and Responsible paper manuscript

Annex 2: Supplement data to Bits or Bricks

Interviewee function	Interviewee Code
Healthcare innovation manager	I1
Health and nursing professional	I2
Healthcare entrepreneur	I3
Project manager	I4
Health and nursing professional	I5
Project manager	I6
Project manager	I7
Healthcare innovation manager	I8
Senior healthcare policy maker	I9
Senior expert healthcare policy and insurance	I10
Senior Health Expert	I11
Managing health and nursing professional	I12

Table 3: Interviews considered in the Bits or Bricks paper manuscript

Annex 3: Supplement data to Talking about Practice

	Guiding question	Aimed at the following factors
Structure	What were the deciding factors for success and which barriers did you discover? Which barriers existed in the implementation phase?	External conditions of action, i.e. the established organisational and institutional configurations
	Which persons, groups or initiatives have enabled the process, and which have rather impeded it?	Constrains and opportunities, system selectivities
	What is the impact on your organisation and for the implementing organisation?	Changes in future configuration and structural change
Practice	What was the initial motivation for the project? What was the consequence of the old approach?	Established practices and problematisation of current routines.
	How did the project start and what happened until today? Which (new) solutions to these problem(s), need(s) or shortcoming(s) does your project offer?	What is the change in practice from past to future through the experiment
	The innovation/project has been fully developed in the future – what changed in the work of the healthcare sector and for the patients? Was the initiative imitated/copied by other organizations or associations? Was it transferred to another context (also in a modified version)?	Future practice and future capacities, scaling and spreading of approach
Agency	What is your background, your role and in which relation do you stand to the project we are discussing?	Learning from past experiences and position to the healthcare system, Initiation process, reflexive use of agency oriented to future system configuration
	How did the project start and what happened until today? What is the core-idea behind the project? Which strategies were pursued by the initiators to implement the innovative solution in the existing context?	Initiation mechanism and implementation. Perceptions of the future
	Which cooperation/partners existed at which stage of the project and what were their roles? Which actors and institutions were crucial in the implementation of the project? Did healthcare professionals, and especially hospitals, play a role in the project implementation? What role did public institutions play in the process?	Distributed agency and networks, reconfiguration of agency and practice

Table 4: A1 Interview structure

Interviewee	Interview code
Senior management in SMS	MI1
Senior management in TBM	MI2
Senior management in TBM	MI3
Innovator and entrepreneur	MI4
Innovator and entrepreneur	MI5
Healthcare professional in SMS	MI6
Innovator and entrepreneur	MI7

Senior Management in SMS	MI8
Innovator and entrepreneur	MI9
Healthcare professional in SMS	MI10
Healthcare professional in SMS	MI11
Senior management in IMIB	MI12
Senior official Murcia Region	MI13
Healthcare professional in SMS	MI14
Senior official Murcia Region	MI15
Innovator and entrepreneur	MI16
Senior management in IMIB	MI17
Patient Organisation Representative	MI18
Patient Organisation Representative	MI19
Senior official Murcia Region	MI20
Senior official in municipality of Örebro	ÖI1
Senior official in municipality of Örebro	ÖI2
Senior official in municipality of Örebro	ÖI3
Innovator and entrepreneur	ÖI4
Senior professional in education system	ÖI5
Senior official in Örebro County	ÖI6
Senior official in Örebro County	ÖI7
CEO of CSO	ÖI8
Senior official in Örebro County	ÖI9
Senior Management in Örebro County	ÖI10
Senior Management in Örebro County	ÖI11
Manager local health centre	ÖI12
Senior official in Örebro County	ÖI13

Table 5: A2 Interviews considered in the Talking about Practice paper

Project code	Description
MP1	The FICHe project pilot, Neuro-at-home, aims at supporting physical rehabilitation of patients through an ICT platform that can be used in a clinical setting or at patients' homes. The platform supports personalised treatment and training plans for patients and gives clinicians the opportunity to follow a higher number of patients.
MP2	The DM4ALL tool, developed during the H2020 project ProEmpower, is a digital healthcare solution that supports diabetes patients in collecting data as a basis for self-management and healthcare professionals to follow and interact with their patients remotely, thus reducing the need for face-to-face meetings.
MP3	The Deep Diver pilot uses Natural Language Processing algorithms on electronic health records to identify Asbestos-related occupational diseases. The algorithms flags healthcare records for review with the aim to support patients in receiving compensation and shifting the costs of treatment to employer financed insurances.

MP4	The EPICO pilot is an App for epileptic patients that aims at improving the patient-doctor communication and supports the self-management of patients. It seeks to improve the patient-doctor relationship through continuous engagement and monitoring, with the aim of preventing crisis and seizures.
MP5	The CHERRIES MS Progress pilot aims at developing a wearable sensor that tracks the movements of multiple sclerosis patients and to detect, building on kinetic algorithms, attacks early. This provides an opportunity for early intervention and prevention of attacks and, thus, slow the progression of the disease.
ÖP1	The Social Investment Fund (SIF) of the Örebro Municipality support the experimentation with new practices and transforms the provision its public services. It introduced a bottom-up change management approach that introduces output legitimacy as contrast to the prevailing input legitimacy of public services.
ÖP2	The SIF project “ <i>Samverkan för teckenspråkiga</i> ” (Collaboration for sign language practitioners) project, supported the labour market integration of people with hearing and cognitive impairment in cooperation with the Activa Foundation, a local CSO. The project resulted in a transformation of public services for this target group.
ÖP3	The <i>Tillsammans för alla barns bästa</i> project, aims to explore the transferability of the Scottish GIRFEC (Getting It Right For Every Child) approach to Örebro. It aims to create an integrated case management on the interface of school, social, and healthcare services, as an early intervention that prevents public expenditure later in life.
ÖP4	The Rehabiliterande Arbetssätt project supports the transition towards close care. The approach moves from compensating for an individual’s lack of abilities to an empowering and rehabilitative approach, which supports a good, healthy and independent life. It builds on output legitimacy and empowering of care providers.
ÖP5	The CHERRIES pilot “Seniors lead Seniors” aims to identify involuntarily lonely elderly people and engage them in co-creating activities of the <i>Seniorkraft</i> programme, which combines social and health related activities. It builds on cooperation between public and CSO actors in providing social and physical activity as a preventive approach.

Table 6: A3 The innovation cases